

CHALLENGES OF PUBLIC EDUCATION IN BRAZIL: the near-universalization of preschool and the differentiation of upper secondary education

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Abstract

This paper analyzes two contrasting developments in Brazilian public education: the near-universalization of preschool and the growing differentiation in upper secondary education. It examines legal reforms and public policies that have expanded access to preschool—especially through the *Proinfância* program—while highlighting persistent regional and racial inequalities. In contrast, upper secondary education has faced increased segmentation due to curricular reforms, unequal investment in differentiated school models (vocational, full-time, and militarized), and lack of public participation. Although recent initiatives like the *Pé-de-Meia* program aim to improve student retention, national education goals remain largely unmet. The paper concludes by emphasizing the urgent need for inclusive, coordinated, and democratic policies to ensure quality education from early childhood through adolescence.

Keywords: right to education, educational inequality, public policy

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**CHALLENGES OF PUBLIC EDUCATION IN BRAZIL:
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secondary education**

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Introduction

1. The Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) arrived in Brazil along with the process of returning to democracy, as we were emerging from a dictatorship that lasted 21 years (1964–1988). The country adhered to this Convention in 1990, accompanied by the accession to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966), which took place in 1992. Therefore, democracy, the expansion of human rights, and the recognition of children's rights go hand in hand.

2. Brazilian education is marked by its complex governance: all three levels of government—Federal Government, States, and Municipalities—are responsible for providing basic education. This means that on the same street or neighborhood, you may find a federal school, a state school, and a municipal school, with enormous differences in the quality of the education provided. This situation is exacerbated by the absence of a National Education System and the lack of a quality standard capable of coordinating this governance, resulting in competition and fragmentation between school networks.

3. Until 1988, compulsory and free education in Brazil covered only elementary education, equivalent to primary education. By the late 1990s, the country had nearly universalized access to this stage, especially benefiting children from the poorest families. In 2009, compulsory schooling was expanded through a constitutional reform and came to cover the entire basic education system, including preschool, elementary, and upper secondary education. It is important to note that this measure covered children and adolescents aged 4 to 17.

4. Analyzing the main reforms carried out since 1988, the year of the current Brazilian Constitution, we can emphasize those that most contributed to this progress, such as: the recognition of rights by the Statute of the Child and Adolescent (Law No. 8,069/1990), the creation of the Basic Education Assessment System (1990), the reorganization of the education system through the National Education Guidelines and Framework Law (Law No. 9,394/1996), the creation of the Fund for the Maintenance and Development of Elementary Education and the Valorization of Teaching (1997), replaced by the Fund for the Maintenance and Development of Basic Education and Valorization of Education

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Professionals (Fundeb), and the requirement for higher education degrees for basic education teachers (1999).

5. Programs supporting school meals, textbooks, school transportation, and direct financial transfers are also considered essential¹.

6. We emphasize that Fundeb (Constitutional Amendment No. 108/2020) is the main financing mechanism of Brazilian education, establishing per-student values for each stage of basic education, financial complementation for the poorest states and municipalities, and conditionalities for access to additional resources based on equity and quality measures.

7. In view of this progress, this contribution to the discussion of the optional protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child is organized into two sections: the first addressing preschool and its near-universalization, and the second addressing upper secondary education and its differentiation, both focusing on the Brazilian experience.

Preschool and its near-universalization

8. Preschool is part of early childhood education, lasts 2 years, and is aimed at children aged 4 and 5. The primary responsibility for providing preschool in Brazil lies with the Municipalities. As a stage of basic education, preschool has been the subject of reforms and new legislation, indicating a prioritization of this theme on the public agenda and evidencing the influence of organized civil society in this process. Since the beginning of the 21st century, we can list the National Curriculum Guidelines for Early Childhood Education (2009), the Legal Framework for Early Childhood (Law No. 13,257/2016), the Common National Curriculum Base for Early Childhood Education (2017), the National Operational Guidelines for Quality and Equity in Early Childhood Education (2024), and the National Quality Parameters for Early Childhood Education (2024).

9. The National Program for Holistic Care for Children and Adolescents (Pronaica in Portuguese) was the first nationwide policy to expand access, including daycare for children aged 0 to 3 and elementary education. The program established the creation and construction of the Centers for Holistic Care for Children and Adolescents (CAIC in Portuguese). These centers were intended to guarantee holistic care for children and adolescents, with physical infrastructure that enabled the provision of integrated services in education, health, social assistance, culture, sports, and leisure. The initial goal was to build 5,000 units, but there is no official information on how many were built.

10. The National Program for the Restructuring and Acquisition of Equipment for the Public School Network of Early Childhood Education (Proinfância in

¹ Almada, J. (2024). *A educação do Brasil: cinco contrapontos necessários*. Sobranceira. Disponível em https://www.ciepp.org/files/ugd/25b93e_360287c6b12341c989104d47b5e7420b.pdf.

Portuguese) was the second nationwide policy to expand access to preschool, also covering daycare centers. Proinfância is still in effect and was more successful than Pronaica. By mid-2022, 8,121 preschool and daycare construction projects had been completed, and 1,843 were under execution, out of a total of 15,732 projects. On the other hand, 2,485 were paralyzed². It became necessary for the Brazilian government to restart and complete these projects; 2,109 were continued and 309 completed to date³.

11. The Continuous National Household Sample Survey (PNAD Contínua in Portuguese)⁴ indicates that 91.5% of children aged 4 and 5 were enrolled in school in Brazil in 2023, that is, they were in preschool. In the same sense, the Monitoring Panel⁵ of the National Education Plan (Law No. 13,005/2014) shows that 93% of children in this age group attended preschool in 2022; the goal was to reach 100% by 2024. This reveals that we have not met the universalization goal, although Proinfância demonstrates a consistent national effort toward achieving it.

12. Proinfância is the main ongoing policy for expanding access to preschool and continues to invest federal resources in the construction of daycare centers and preschools in Brazilian municipalities.

13. Therefore, the following remain as challenges for free and public preschool education in Brazil: (i) regional and local inequalities, with lower access to preschool in states and municipalities of the North and Center-West Regions, some of which are part of the Amazon; (ii) ethno-racial inequalities, with lower access for Black, Brown, and Indigenous children compared to White children; (iii) inefficiency in expanding school infrastructure to meet demand for public daycare and preschools, due to delays in construction, corruption in the use of public funds, and weak planning for enrollment and criteria for the allocation of school places; (iv) the provision of low-quality private daycare and preschools, often with public funding, involving irregularities and reports of misuse; and (v) the monitoring and enforcement of the various legal frameworks that guarantee children the right to quality early childhood education.

² Coelho, J., Sakai, J., & Galdino, M. (2022). *Relatório Tá de Pé 2022: Análise da construção de obras de escolas e creches públicas financiadas pelo governo federal*. Transparência Brasil. https://www.transparencia.org.br/downloads/publicacoes/relatorio_tdp_2022.pdf.

³ Fundo Nacional de Desenvolvimento da Educação. (2023). *Pacto Nacional pela Retomada de Obras da Educação*. <https://www.gov.br/fnde/pt-br/acao-a-informacao/acoes-e-programas/programas/par/pacto-nacional-pela-retomada-de-obras-da-educacao>.

⁴ Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística. (2023). *Pesquisa Nacional por Amostra de Domicílios Contínua (PNAD Contínua): Educação 2023 – Resultados referentes à pré-escola e ao ensino médio*. <https://www.ibge.gov.br/estatisticas/sociais/educacao/17270-pnad-continua.html>.

⁵ Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais Anísio Teixeira. (2024). *Painel de Monitoramento do Plano Nacional de Educação – PNE: Resultados de 2022*. <https://www.gov.br/inep/pt-br/acao-a-informacao/dados-abertos/inep-data/painel-de-monitoramento-do-pne>.

Upper secondary education and its differentiation

14. Upper secondary education is the final stage of basic education, lasts 3 years, and should be attended by adolescents aged 15 to 17. The primary responsibility for providing upper secondary education in Brazil lies with the States. This level was the subject of a curricular reform in 2016 (Law No. 13,415/2017). This reform was decided in a centralized manner, without listening to teachers, students, and their families. The central idea was that these young people could choose and organize their own curriculum. The implementation of the reform was taken over by corporate foundations and faced strong resistance from the educational community, civil society, and teachers' union. Studies and research conducted in recent years have proven that the promised freedom of choice was not realized, the curricular offerings became limited, especially affecting the most vulnerable students, promises to improve school infrastructure were not fulfilled, and educational inequalities between public and private schools deepened⁶. This led to the suspension of the reform in 2023 and its revision in 2024 through Law No. 14,945/2024, whose developments are still underway.

15. The policies for upper secondary education have adopted differentiation as their main feature - that is, parallel and differentiated schools have been created and strengthened, focusing on vocational education, full-time education, and militarized education. It is notable that these schools received greater investment and improved their infrastructure compared to other public schools. This differentiation creates a segmented educational system, in which part of the students have access to better conditions, undermining the idea of the right to quality education for all.

16. The vocational education policy was implemented through the National Program for Access to Technical Education and Employment (Pronatec in Portuguese), in actions such as the expansion of the Federal Network for Professional, Scientific and Technological Education Institutions, the Brazil Professionalized Program to support state technical schools, the e-Tec Brazil Network offering technical courses via distance learning, the Agreement on Free Services with the National Learning Services, and the Training Grant program. Without altering this set of initiatives, a new strategy is being implemented to expand enrollments in state networks through the Program for the Full Payment of State Debts (Complementary Law No. 212/2025), which proposes exchanging state debt with the Union in return for the establishment of new vocational education enrollments.

⁶ Associação Nacional de Pós-Graduação e Pesquisa em Educação. (2023). *Relatório final: Seminários ANPEd Ensino Médio - O que as pesquisas têm a dizer*. https://legado.anped.org.br/sites/default/files/images/relatorio_final_-_seminarios_anped_ensino_medio_-_o_que_as_pesquisas_tem_a_dizer_-_aprovado_28-06.pdf.

17. The full-time education policy was implemented through two programs: the Program for the Promotion of Full-Time Secondary Schools (2017) and the Full-Time School Program (Law No. 14,640/2023), both involving substantial federal financial transfers so that States and Municipalities can create full-time enrolments. The main characteristic of the Brazilian school day is that it occurs in a single shift, either in the morning or afternoon. These programs aim to extend the school day to at least 7 hours per day.

18. The national militarized education policy was short-lived. The National Program of Civic-Military Schools (PECIM in Portuguese) was created in 2019 and revoked in 2023. Military personnel were assigned to manage public schools, implementing military-style discipline and taking on functions traditionally performed by teachers and school principals. There is segregation of students who do not adapt or conform to military norms. This militarized model was denounced nationally and internationally and is currently under review by the Federal Supreme Court, Brazil's constitutional court. Nevertheless, some Brazilian states—such as Paraná, Mato Grosso, Roraima, Maranhão, and Bahia—continue to adopt and expand this model, which poses a threat to the foundational civilian nature of public education in Brazil.

19. The Continuous National Household Sample Survey (PNAD Contínua) shows that 91.9% of adolescents aged 15 to 17 were enrolled in school in Brazil in 2023, that is, in upper secondary education. Similarly, the Monitoring Panel of the National Education Plan (Law No. 13,005/2014) shows that 76.9% of adolescents in this age group attended upper secondary education or had completed basic education in 2022; the goal was to reach 85% by 2024. This is one of the reasons why there are approximately 10.3 million young people aged 15 to 29 who are neither studying nor working, especially Black or Brown women. Although we reached 2.2 million enrollments in vocational upper secondary education in 2023, we are far from the goal of 4.8 million enrollments by 2024. Lastly, 19.7% of upper secondary students were enrolled in full-time education in 2023, but the goal was 25% by 2024, and it is unlikely to be achieved.

20. The Pé-de-Meia Program (Law No. 14,818/2024) is one of the main actions to improve retention indicators for upper secondary students and encourage them to continue their studies. The program consists of providing monthly and annual financial incentives to students in situations of socioeconomic vulnerability throughout upper secondary education.

21. Thus, the following remain as challenges for free and public upper secondary education in Brazil: (i) the differentiation between school networks, which threatens the principle of universality in public schooling, aggravating educational inequalities that especially affect the most vulnerable students; (ii) the lack of focus in upper secondary policies, which open simultaneous fronts and disperse public resources across multiple programs; (iii) the implementation of curricular reforms without the participation of key stakeholders - that is, students

and teachers; (iv) the militarization of public schools, which threatens the civilian nature of public schools and undermines their mission of educating for citizenship and democracy, devalues teachers' work, and places military personnel in roles that are not theirs; (v) the ineffectiveness and disarticulation of this set of policies in promoting youth engagement in upper secondary education.